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Contents

S. No.	Title / Author(s)	Page No.
01	Surrogate Advertising-Softly Promoting Hard Product <i>Dr.S. Usha and A.V.R. Akshaya</i>	67-72
02	Ethics in Marketing Research <i>N. Prasanna Kumar</i>	73-82
03	An ISM Approach for Modeling the Barriers of Reverse Logistics Practices: A Case Study of Indian Business Environment <i>Arvind Jayant</i>	83-102
04	Consumers Preference towards Purchasing Pattern of Cause Related Marketing Products with Special Reference to Coimbatore City <i>R. Sudha and Dr. D. Elangovan</i>	103-112
05	Emerging Construction of Work-Life Balance: The Experience of Employees in a Call-Centre Environment in Villupuram <i>D. Shoba and Dr.G. Suganthi</i>	113-123

Emerging Construction of Work–Life Balance: The Experience of Employees in a Call-Centre Environment in Villupuram

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Abstract— Work–life balance, as a crucial aspect of employee and organizational wellness, remains an interesting field of research, especially due to the changing demographic employee profile. The objective of the study was to explore employees' construction of work–life balance in a customer care environment. This qualitative study was designed from an interpretive perspective. Ten employees, selected through purposeful sampling, participated in the study. Data was gathered through in-depth interviews and grounded theory was applied during data analysis. The grounded theory analysis of the data yielded six themes central to participants construction of work–life balance. The findings suggest that work–life balance is conceptualized as a continuous, subjective and holistic valuation of satisfaction derived from multiple roles in relation to the importance to the individual at a given point in time. Findings provide valuable managerial information to guide suitable strategies enhancing the work–life balance experience and by implication employees' general wellbeing, job satisfaction and commitment. This study contributes to the evolving body of knowledge with regard to work–life balance and provides a unique context-specific perspective to the conceptual understanding of the construct.

Keywords— Employee Wellness, Grounded Theory, In-Depth Interview, Qualitative Research, Quality of Lifework–Home Interaction

I. INTRODUCTION

Under an employed individual Research, the work and life (or family life) is the two most important concepts in the Organizational environment. In International scenario employee and organizational wellness was brought through work–life balance and it has directed a significant shift towards work place, work–life balance and quality of life. Work–life balance issues reflect an increased interest in research and literature in the past decade internationally and in work–home interface. Furthermore, in studies the constructions of work life balance are explored, researchers need to have several different approaches to define systematic practically and measure the Conceptual construction difference is also apparent in the variety of related parlance that is used to denote work–life balance, for example work/family interaction work/family alignment work/life balance and work–home interface.

This Research emphasized generally on work–life balance issues from a gender outlook from a outlook of employees with parental care level belongingness; and from an age outlook relatively little focus on the special consideration work–life balance experiences of employees in different race groups is apparent. In this study, we found significant differences in the work-life interaction among the different socio- economic and cultural groups.

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II. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The introductory discussion highlights the conceptual differences that exist in the work-life balance research concepts as well as the generally quantitative research outlook in this field in Villupuram. This research has been initialized by some basic need for concept clarification of work-life balance. For consistency in executing our research, we decided to use the term 'work-life balance' as opposed to work-family interaction interface.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

From the introductory discussion to this article it is clear that concept clarification of work-life balance remains a complex, yet necessary, pursuit. In qualitative research, according to both Morse[17] and Kelly [11], a theoretical review is, however, not only used to focus the research, but also to provide the opportunity for a critical theoretical comparison in developing conceptual outcomes, such as is intended with this study. In the following literature review, we therefore reflect on evolving perspectives on the construction of work-life balance, which have over the past decade introduced a paradigm shift to conventional perspectives thereof. As such, our analysis of the data was also influenced by both past and more recent conceptions of the construct and it is in this light that the following review of relevant conceptual literature is presented. The interest in work-life balance originates from perspective semphasising conflict between work and family roles, and

According to Roberts[23] overwork was initially identified as the primary reason for work-life balance problems. This perspective probably contributed to[16] earlier opinion that work-life conflict results when mutually incompatible pressures are experienced in work and family roles. The continued interest in work-life balance issues focused in particular on married woman entering the job market, on dual-career couples and single-parent households (Van Aarde & Mostert[28]). A review of the literature reveals that earlier perspectives on work-life balance were dominated by rather negative perceptions of the impact that work has on family (Eagle et al[2].Greenhaus et al[7] Mostert[18]). While some researchers began to recognize the bi-directional nature of work and family demands[21], earlier studies in general focused more on spillover effects from work to family than on family-to-work influence (Froncet al., [5] Fu& Shaffer[6]).

According to Mostert[18],the past decade has seen a renewed interest in work-life balance experiences. In general, this is again due to more demographic changes in the labour profile, but also specifically to increasing workforce diversity facilitated by legislated employment equity and affirmative action drives. However, changing paradigms about work on the one hand, and more ambiguous boundaries between work and family spheres on the other, also seem to be contributing to a change in the work-life balance research focus. Research focusing on the negative impact from work to home is based on negative assumptions about work and its meaning to the employee. Such negative perceptions about work and its impact on the family role lead to work-life balance interventions narrowly emphasising either a reduction in working hours or more flexible working hours (Roberts[23]).

Eikhof et al.[3] state that premised on negative and reductionist assumptions about work, the work-life balance debate fails to capture more varied employee attitudes to and engagement with work'. Recent research calls for a changed perspective, recognising the fact that work may be a source of satisfaction and an opportunity for growth and fulfilment for people (see Eikhof et al,)[3]. Inspired by the assumption that work may evoke positive feelings of

competence and wellbeing, Mostert et al [18] also recommend a stronger focus on exploring positive work-to-family interaction.

IV. RESEARCH DESIGN

A. Research Setting and Sampling

The study was conducted in the call-centre section of the Southern tech in villupuram. In line with Marshall and Rossman[16], who told that a study conducted under the complexity environment, Hit and miss sampling was used. When new themes were no longer emerging, data saturation was achieved, with 10 employees finally having participated in the data-gathering process. Small samples were collected for appropriate and qualitative research so as to enhance relationship between the researcher and participants, and to allow an indepth interpretive exploration of the research.

Table 1

Profile of Participants

Potential participants were contacted through where the Permission obtained from the management of the customer care department to conduct the study. The participants also agreed to participate in the study and individual interviews were set up.

Data-Gathering

Qualitative methods of data collection are favoured by researchers working with interpretive and constructionist paradigms (Terre Blanche & Durrheim[27]). For this study, the semi-structured in-depth interview (Kvale)[14] was used as the main method of data collection. Based on an initial review of relevant literature, an interview guide was prepared to give structure and guidance to the interview (Marshall & Rossman[16]; Stroh[26]). A pilot interview was conducted, after which the interview guide was adjusted to focus on eliciting core work-life balance experiences.

Data Analysis

The grounded theory approach was used to analyze the data following the steps of open coding, axial coding and selective coding in an iterative and flexible manner (Locke[15], Pandit[19], Strauss & Corbin[25]). The transcribed interviews represented the main source for the open coding phase in the study. During open coding, data was fractured into smaller concepts and categories, and no conscious attempt was made to interpret the data or extract themes from the data. During axial coding, the focus was on identifying possible relationships between initially coded concepts and categories in order to develop main categories or themes from the data and their sub-categories (Pandit[19]). Selective coding is the process of selecting the central theme/s integrating all other inferred themes or main categories (Strauss & Corbin[25]).

Strategies Employed to Ensure Quality Data

Credibility and transferability of the study were enhanced by establishing an audit trail of the data through digital recording and verbatim transcriptions as well as process notes spanning data collection and data analyses[31]. As recommended by Marshall and Rossman[16], interpretations made in this study are consistently grounded in the raw data by providing verbatim substantiation to themes presented. Silverman[24] also suggests that applying a particular analytical model, such as grounded theory, enhances the transferability of the findings. Silverman[24] explains that good research goes back to the participants with the tentative results and refines them in the light of the participants' reactions. After data analyses, member validation was done, allowing participants to reflect on their personal contributions in relation to the interpretations of the data. In addition, a peer review of the data was conducted by another researcher.

Reporting

In congruence with a more modernist, qualitative research perspective, the reporting style employed is more objective and neutral than personal and reflexive. Furthermore, in reporting on the findings, conceptual interpretations are substantiated with verbatim excerpts from the data and integrated with relevant theory as suggested by Locke[15], that the presentation of results should 'weave together data incidents and theoretical elements'.

V. FINDINGS

From the 48 themes that were initially extracted during the open coding phase, six themes central to the construction of work-life balance by participants were ultimately identified. These themes are discussed below as representing the meaning that participants attach to work-life balance. As integrity in reporting results requires a demonstration that the explanations and conclusions presented are generated from, and grounded in, the data (Ritchie & Lewis[22]), themes are substantiated by verbatim extracts from the data. An integration of the data with existing literature also forms part of the discussion, further confirming the relevance and integrity of interpretations made.

A. Theme 1: An Interaction between Multiple Roles

As is evident in the abundant literature on work-life balance, balance becomes a problem due to potentially conflicting expectations in different work-life roles and having to divide scarce resources between specifically the work role and the family role. Participants also frequently referred to balancing the work role and the family role in particular. As an example, one participant mentions:

I believe that I have a balance. For me, when I am at work, I give 100 percent towards my job. When I am at home, family life for me is extremely important, extremely.

And another participant states:

I try to ensure that my life or day's life is partitioned equally and proportionately to what my work requires of me, as well as what my family also requires of me.

Mostert et al [18] refer to work-home interaction as an interactive process of combining work and family roles and demands and in which a person's functioning in either one of these two roles impacts on the other (Greenhaus et al [7], Mostert et al [18]). Although multiple roles is clearly a factor in work-life balance (Kalliath & Brough) [10], Heraty et al. [9] mention that historically research in the field was usually either from a family-focused perspective or a work focused perspective. In line with Parkes et al [20] as well as Lee and Steele's broader perspectives on work roles versus non work roles (rather than the work versus family role), participants clearly indicated the importance of the self as an additional role in the work-life balance equation. A participant explained that balance is the opportunity to do what he wants to do in a period of time that he sets – giving himself personal space or breathing time:

Balance is not just about me and the family, it is also about my own time, you know; sometimes I just need to be by myself and that is how I deal with stuff. (page number not for citation purposes)

The need for personal time is also reflected in the following response from another participant:

'For me, it is make the sacrifice, but reward yourself at that particular period in time.' The general multiplicity of roles is further evident in the following:

Data indicates clearly that balance is not just about work and family roles. It is also about having personal and leisure time, attending to spiritual roles and other physical needs. When considering the construction of work-life balance, the findings therefore confirm the interaction between multiple roles as core to our understanding of work-life balance. Interacting with, and reflecting on, issues of the self are additionally emphasized as being crucial to the work-life balance equation, and the multiple role perspective should explicitly include the self as a key role with expectations and demands to be considered.

B. Theme 2: Valuing the Quality of Work-life Dynamics

Analysis of work-life balance experiences reveals an underlying activity in which one is consistently evaluating the extent of satisfaction derived from multiple life roles. In judging their work-life balance, some participants seemed more concerned with the quality of the balance in their life, rather than with the frequency of balance. One participant explained that for him

Don't try and get balance everyday because something will happen so then you have nothing to look forward to because you are trying to do it every single day. I look at it from the quality; like I said, you know, there is a frequency how often I am going to do it, and if once a year is fine for me, it is how much I get out of that

Once a year as opposed to doing it every day.

Participants also explained that work-life balance should not necessarily have time boundaries; rather, it should be outcomes based:

I shouldn't have the time boundary. A lot of projects, a lot of environments have become outcomes-based. It is like I have got to deliver on stuff, and I have got to manage my time in order to deliver it by a specific date.

International perspectives on work–life balance seem to be moving away from an overemphasis on flexible work schedules as the only solution to work–life balance issues. Eikhof et al[3] seriously criticise such a perspective as being grounded in the assumption that all people are more or less negative about work and need more time with their families. Time management alone and the division of time are therefore no longer adequate in defining or addressing work–life balance (Robert[40]). Lee and Steele note that research is moving towards the recognition of potential enrichment or facilitation amongst multiple roles, which may buffer negative work–life balance experiences. From the data it is clear that although flexibility of work hours positively contributes to work–life balance, it is rather the quality of experience in different life spheres that is of value to participants. Depending on their assessment of these quality outcomes, participants frame a positive or negative perception of the work–life balance.

C. Theme 3: Work–life Balance is subjectively experienced

From the data it is also clear that participants' needs differ and therefore work–life balance seems to be a subjective experience, since people differentiate their balance in terms of their needs and expectations in different life roles. Some participants emphasise the importance of family over work: 'Work is not the most important; family is obviously more important to me, but work is priority'; and:

I do not think there is anything worse than your home life being upset, because if your home life is upset, nothing else works for you. You can be the greatest person in your career, you can be the best, most educated, most learned, most well-organized person at work but if you are not okay at home, believe me you are not going to perform the way you want to perform at work or the way you can perform.

Contrary to the findings above, Greenhaus et al[7] present a very objective and inflexible perspective to work–life balance in that they suggest that balance is obtained when equal time and involvement are put into both the work and family roles and when equal satisfaction is derived from these roles. However, in more recent commentaries, Poelmans et al[21]. And Roberts[23] emphasise that every individual experiences work–life balance in a different way. They concur that balance is inextricably linked to satisfaction, which is a subjective phenomenon and as such argue that balance needs to be assessed as a function of a person's priorities or individual differences. Eikhof et al[3] cite various studies indicating different antecedents of work–life balance, which suggest that work–life balance is not an objective observation of someone else's life, but a subjective experience of the individual. The finding that work–life balance is a subjective experience also relates to the perspective that individuals perceive their multiple roles as varying in importance (salience); and therefore assessment of work–life balance will change over time in relation to one's life and career development stages (Kalliath & Brough, [10]; Parkes et al[20]).

D. Theme 4: A Holistic experience of Multiple Role Satisfaction/Fulfillment

According to Eikhof et al[3] "research over the years has revealed that only some workers experience work and life as separate and balanceable. For other workers, work and life are intertwined, even amalgamated, so that they cannot or do not want to distinguish and disentangle work and life".

(Eikenhof et al[3]) They emphasise that work–life balance perspectives need to progress to a more holistic understanding of life in which work and life are regarded as positive and enabling experiences. Similarly one participant emphasises that his work and family roles overlap:

“Reasonably I cannot give 100 percent to my work. I would love to do this. If you are a family man, you cannot do that... obviously the one would overlap with the other, and you know when you start feeling the pressure coming from work; then you learn to focus more on work, and vice versa as well”

Numerous positive experiences of participants’ work roles were evident in the data and confirmed the evolving perspective that work–life balance is a holistic experience of multiple roles as opposed to splitting life into multiple boxes with spillover effects from the one to the other. In stating that ‘I will never look for a routine environment, you know, so if it is challenging, that is the drive that keeps me interested, keeps you on high alert’, a participant emphasises that the need to work does not inhibit or replace the need to have a family. Similarly another says:

“ I think it all depends on an individual how you take it. If you are passionate about your work, you will give more and you will be willing to do it without any problem.

A participant also expressed the need to grow in his career but also to have the opportunity to live out his family role. He states that he needs ‘to develop and grow [in his career] and you know for me to be able to do what I need to do for them [his family] as well’.

The holistic experience of fulfilment or satisfaction is also emphasised by Kirchmeyer[12] (Kalliath & Brough)[10] describes it as achieving satisfying experiences in and across all life domains. In this regard a participant referred to work–life balance as achieving personal growth: ‘I would say I view it as, you know, it contributes towards your personal growth. You grow as a person, so it is more of personal growth.’ Various other literature resources also refer to satisfaction or fulfilment across multiple roles as being implicit to the work–life balance experience (Parkes et al[20],); and some also refer to personal growth as implicit in achieving balance (Kalliath & Brough)[10]. In conclusion, our understanding of work–life balance therefore confirms that work and family roles as well as the role of self and other potential life roles are not mutually exclusive and clearly separable. Rather these roles are intertwined and as a result a person will experience work–life balance as a holistic valuation of the quality outcomes of multiple role interaction.

E. Theme 5: A Continuous Life Process

Kalliath and Brough[10] suggest that levels of work–life balance in a person’s life change overtime due to the differentiation of role needs and expectations linked to developmental tasks over one’s life span. Such a life stage perspective is also evident in the following response:

“Some people really do not have work–life balance and they have kids and things like that and it does get hard. So I think I am sitting in a better position now that I do not really have all those responsibilities yet. But I do believe when I do that work–life balance is going to be so much more important”.

Kalliath and Brough [10] agree that role salience not only varies across life and work roles, but also changes over time within those roles; and that continuous adjustment to multiple demands across at least the period of employment is a more realistic view of work-life balance. Kofidimos[22] (Poelmans et al[21]) states that most people regard work-life balance as ephemeral requiring a never-ending balancing act of multiple demands,[37]. Define work-life balance as 'a continuous process of creating harmony between work, family and personal life'. Finally Koekemoeret al[13] conclusion that individuals may alternate their emphases on work and family activities in the short run to achieve balance in the long run is emphasized in the words of a participant: 'Don't try and get balance every day... it is how much I get out of that once a year as opposed to doing it every day.'

F. Theme 6: A Managing Competence

Contemporary definitions of management emphasise planning (including prioritization and scheduling). The organizing of resources and control are core competencies in effective management. Various participant responses indicated that management of multiple role dynamics is essential in working towards work-life balance. Specifically role prioritization, time management and establishing support structures (organizing resources) were referred to as key activities in attempts to achieve work-life balance.

Results indicate that participants who were able to prioritise and schedule time efficiently experienced greater balance. One person explicitly said about work-life balance that 'it goes with planning and prioritising' and another confirmed that work-life balance is not attained by poor planning: 'I would say poor planning, because if everything was planned properly in the beginning then we would have that because you would actually be able to plan your life.' Furthermore, the need to priorities roles appears to be influenced by the individual participants' values and goals and the varying importance they place on work and family roles. As such some participants emphasized prioritization both between the work and family roles as well as within each role:

So it is about prioritizing also, but when you also get home you need to prioritize and say, this is the family time; I have to do the family responsibilities and chores first and then get to the work thing, so it is a question of just mingling around responsibilities when you get to the other side, I don't have a set formula that I am using. I just play it by what is more pressing or what is more urgent at the point in time and prioritize from there.

Similarly time management is an essential component of managing balance:

If I spend too much time at work, it could make things at home suffer... I have been at a point where I give more of my time to work, and you start becoming a stranger in your own home; you need to find balance.

With regard to organizing resources to assist in achieving work-life balance, all of the participants identified their family support structures (mother, siblings, grandparents, in-laws) as being helpful and supportive with regard to work emergencies. Some emphasise support structures at home:

I will have a similar support structure in place at home, but not only with my immediate family, but with my second family, like for instance my mother, or fiancé's mother or my brother or my sister.

The existence and extent of support structures are instrumental in the experience of work-life balance and these include spouses, grandparents, parents, cousins and siblings(8); Robles9.).

This finding is consistent with research indicating that supervisor support reduces strain and behavior-based work to-family conflict (Batt & Valcour[1],; Fu & Shaffer[6],) this indicates the importance of team members as a support system in work-life balance experiences.

VI. DISCUSSION

Due to the conceptual debate in the work-life balance literature as well as limited conceptual research in the Villupuram work context, the aim of this study was to explore the work-life balance construction of employees in a South African call centre environment. Motivated by Franks et al[4], employees in full-time employment were sampled. In summary, interpretation of the data produced the following six themes central to explaining work-life balance as constructed by participants in this study (and integrated with relevant theoretical perspectives on the construct):

- an interaction between multiple roles
- valuing the quality of work-life dynamics
- work-life balance is subjectively experienced
- a holistic experience of multiple role satisfaction/fulfilment
- a continuous life process
- a managing competence.

In integrating these themes to produce a central theoretical perspective, we conclude the following: work-life balance for a sample of call-centre employees seems to be best explained by the fact that it manifests as a subjective and holistic valuation of work-life dynamics in relation to the proportionate importance the individual attaches to multiple roles. As such, work-life balance is regarded as a lifelong process of consistently evaluating the quality of multiple work-life role outcomes in relation to one another. This continuous process implies a challenge to the individual in that it entails building competence to efficiently manage the interaction between multiple roles. From the results, it seems evident that the conceptual debate underlying work-life balance as a construct is substantiated. Traditional perspectives regarding work-life balance based on employees' experiences of work and family as separate entities, and in which work has a predominantly negative impact on the family, were not evident in the data. Work-life balance seems rather to be the result of acknowledging multiple roles in life (not just work and family) and that satisfaction in all life roles contributes to the experience of balance. Furthermore balance seems to be subjectively judged by each individual- a judgment that is influenced by each particular life stage, which again determines the importance of various life roles in relation to one another. Based on these findings, using the term 'work-life balance' may no longer be appropriate as the construct in itself implies a dichotomous nature between work and life. In contradiction, participants clearly indicated that their lives incorporate work as a very important role impacting positively on their experience of balance. As such, we believe that referring to work/non-work balance may constitute a more appropriate conceptualization of employees' holistic experience of balance in their lives.

The study contributes to the evolving conceptual understanding of work-life balance in a changing world of work, bearing in mind that it provides a context-specific perspective to the conceptual understanding thereof due to the sample parameters. Still, similarities between the results and conceptual reviews provide some evidence that traditional work-life balance perspectives are changing, and should be incorporated in future explorations of the work and non-work dynamics. The results of this study further provide potentially practical and valuable information to organizational leaders and human resource managers in a call-centre environment. Insights gained can facilitate implementing suitable strategies to enhance work/non-work balance experiences and as such garner employees' general well being, job satisfaction and commitment. Finally, the study was found to be valuable by participants in that it increased their self-awareness regarding work/non-work balance and as such lead to the generation of alternative solutions to manage the challenges they face in integrating their multiple roles.

VII. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

Although the findings cannot be transferred to other work environments, they prove meaningful for the purpose of this study. Research replicating the present study in different organizational contexts will also help to enhance our understanding of unique work/non-work balance experiences and facilitate the development and implementation of more appropriate balance policies and strategies in the 21st century world of work. Longitudinal studies would furthermore add significant insight to understanding an individual's subjective experiences of work/non-work balance over time.

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